

A psychological review of the Srimad Bhagavad Geeta

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Abstract:

The sacred Geeta is not only a book of religion and philosophy but also a timeless clinical guide to psychiatry. Most of the great writer, philosopher, atomic scientist, critic, intellectual, academician, scholar, pioneer India & world criticised about the Geeta. However although the field of western psychology has expanded in this way. Verse 700 of the Geeta there are 18th chapters it has two speakers. The main speaker is Lord Krishna and the main listener is Arjuna. The secondary speaker is Sanjoy and the secondary listener is Dhritarashtra.

Respectively, in the first chapter of the Geeta, psychological problems are expressed through Arjuna . The treatment of their mental disorder is started by Lord Krishna in the eleventh verse of the second chapter fear and anxiety are the main source of depression among the fears deaths is the most frightening . The Geeta begins with the knowledge of the inequality of the soul, psychological medicine also includes, cognitive therapies to treat mental illness. For the realization of self-knowledge, self-realization of life is not possible until wisdom consciousness arises ignorance obscures the meaning of life. The Geeta begins with sadness the complete opposite salvation, light on one side and the darkness on the other. The dark side of the mind is called 'sadness' and the light side is called 'supreme peace' or bliss for life.

So my Research paper discussed introduction part of the Geeta is not only ordinary book I established as a very significant part of our life, other part I discussed origin as development of Indian psychology and analytical study of core part & psychological review of the Geeta and lastly as a result will be focus Lord Krishna is the first psychologist in the world . we have limited the Geeta devotion and bound to universal eternal possibilities with emotion. This is the opposite of Geeta worship analytical empirical interpretation and application of the Geeta should be introduced to make the traditional method of trading the Geeta dynamic and practical in today's society.

Keywords: Psychology, Geeta, Sadness, Peach

Introduction:

The Geeta, which originated on the eve of the Battle of Kurukshetra, dates back to around 2500 BC. The present edited form of the Geeta, consisting of 700 verses, was probably completed in 500-400 BC¹.

The incomparable appreciation of the ideals of the Geeta among Western intellectuals brought up in modern civilization as well as in Asia is very important and a matter of great pride for Indians and ultimately for Hindus in 1745, Charles Bilkins made the first English translation and interpretation of the Geeta. A valuable preface was written by Warren Hastings. The Geeta has been translated by the philosophers George Friedrich Hegel, Arthur Schopenhauer, J.H. Mc Carthy, and others. G.S. Harder, Paul Duchene, Herman von ,Kechaling, the linguist Humboldt², the famous writer Balt Whitman, Aldox Huxley, Christopher Isherod, the mystic Bodolf Steiner, the leader of the Theosophy Society Anne Besant In addition, the famous Nobel Prize-winning poet and play wright T.S. Eliot said: "That balance of mind which which a highly civilized individual such as Arjuna, the hero of the Bhagawat Geeta can maintain in ac-tion³" J.W. Howar, a German Sanskrit scholar and pioneer of yoga teaching, wrote: "The Geeta gives us not only profound insight that are valid for all times and for all religious life. Here spirit is at work belongs to

our spirit⁴" The German philosopher who translated the Geeta into Latin. W.Schlegel writes in the introduction. "O thou sacred singer....I salute thee above all singers and I worship unceas-ing by the trace of thy footsteps⁵"The famous American writer David Thoreau considered the Geeta to he commented on the Geeta: "In the morning I bathe my intellect in the stupendous and cosmological philosophy of the Bhagavad Geeta⁶" Apart from these, the scientist Einstein and the atomic scientist Oppenhammer also respected and studied the Geeta with reverence. The Geeta is not only a book of religion and philosophy but also, a timeless clinical guide to Psychiatry.

Origins and Development of Indian Psychology:

Indian psychology is very ancient and different from modern Western Psychology. Modern Western psychology is still divided into many branches. Its independent discipline has only emerged since 1879, but the peace of development has been very rapid and several communities have emerged in the name of psychology. However, although the field of Western Psychology has expanded in this way, it remains confined to a limitation. This is because this stream of psychology is limited to the study of mental processes such as sensation, anxiety, perception, imagination, judgment. Memory, etc. and the physical causes and physical conditions that produce them. They believe

that all the knowledge we have acquired is only a charge of excitement generated by nerves in specific centers of the brain in collaboration with the senses. They regard mental thoughts and feelings as the actions and reactions of the physical theory of the brain. "They believe that sensation and consciousness are the functions of the cerebral cortex of the brain. The brain they do not acknowledge that there is a separate entity called mind or soul besides actions"⁷ On the other hand, the views of Modern Psychology are Western.

Incorporated in the style of psychology, the traditional time less flow is understood. However many western scholars who have studied Indian yoga such as George Feuberstein Ken Wilber Jabald Jemes Larson, Bosc Printe etc. Have left behind many valuable writings respecting the timeless flow of Indian Psychology⁸ the flow of Indian psychology begins in the Rig Veda, the oldest book in the world⁹ and its movement is embedded in the spiritual practices of Hinduism, Buddhism and Jainism Indian psychology emphasizes the physical body and the five senses as well as the mind as the sixth sense and Beyond it the soul, the three elements (sattva, Raja, tama), the five cells, etc. For the study of human behaviour or personality. He also discovered the techniques of Knowledge, devotion and karma yoga for the attainment of a strong body, healthy mind and spiritual welfare. It is expanded in the Upanishadic texts. The Agama scriptures of Jainism, such as the Sthanga, Sutakritanga and Bhagavati sutra, discuss psychology in detail¹⁰ He has reviewed the analysis of psychology in meditation -orientated works such as Dharmmapada of Buddhist Literature and the Abhidharma kosha¹¹ with a very extensive and serious insight. Mental illness treatment is extensively discussed in Ayurvedic texts such as Charaka and Sushruta. The Atharav Veda was the source of Ayurvedic treatment of mental illness. The purpose of the Atharve Veda is to guide the means of human welfare. According to this Veda, there are four physical elements in the human personality Vata, Pitta, Sleshma and Kaph. These four principles are the state of good health. Therefore, it is important to understand the importance of the three modes of nature (Sattva, Raja and Tama) in the development of a healthy and strong personality¹² Yoga is essential in the Indian educational tradition to build a healthy and strong personality. Hatha. Yoga, Mantra Yoga, Laya Yoga, Karma-Bhakti-Jnana Yoga etc. Were invented by Indian sages to give fulfillment to life. The review of the psychology occupies a vast field in the Nyaya of Rishi Gautama, the Vedanta Of Vadranya, the Mimamsa of Jaimini, the Yoga of Patanjali and the Vaisheshika philosophy of Kanda¹³ This Indian philosophy can be called psycho spiritual technology in modern terms. According to the

Western yogi, Gorge Forten opinion ancient Indian psychology was 'psychospiritual technology in applied knowledge and wisdom. The larger evolutionary destiny of mankind by fostering the psycho spiritual maturation of the individual'¹⁴.

From the mid-19th century, Ramakrishna Paramahansa, Swami Vivekananda, Rabindranath Tagore, Mahatma Gandhi and Sri Arvind Focused on Indian psychiatry. In modern times, Indian methods were welcomed abroad for the treatment of mental and emotional illnesses. The success of the treatment was praised abroad and a revolution began. Mahesh Yogi's T.M. (Transcendental Meditation) Swami Yogananda's Kriyayoga and some of the methods compiled by Acarya Rajni are very popular abroad.

Psychological Review of the Geeta:

Verse 700 Of the Geeta. There are 18 chapters. It has two speakers one is the main and the other is the secondary. Similarly, there are two listeners. One is the main and the other is the secondary. The main speaker is Lord Krishna and the man listener is Arjuna The secondary speaker is Sanjaya and the secondary listener is Dhritarashtra.

The first chapter of the Geeta is called Visada Yoga and Mokshayoga seen that the word means liberation from all mental feel the bliss of salvation. Therefore, it can be suffering. The introduction of the Geeta begins With sadness, the complete opposite of salvation. Light on one Side and darkness on the other, It is impossible for these two to exist together. The existence of one The disappearance of the other is Inevitable. Like day and night, he last chapter, the eighteen chapter, is called, there are two sides to the mental world. The dark side of the mind is called 'sadness' and the light side is called superme peace or bliss sorrow arises from ignorance and bliss, arises from the light of wisdom so wise people are never sad. Just as darkness must have the opposite of light, So must just have the opposite of bliss as darkness is the source of the search for light, so Sadness is the source of the search for bliss for life. The search for the bliss of the Geeta begins with such a psychological analysis. There is a Psychological analysis involved in the blindness of Dhritarashtra. This Blindness is symbolic. According to Indian Psychology, humans have three eyes, Blood is the fleshy gross eye.

The eye of Wisdom or the third eye is also called Shivanetra. Ken Wilber in his books The Spectrum of consciousness, The Atma Project, A transpersonal View of human development, Up from Eden, A transpersonal View of human evolution, eye to eye and The Quest for the new paradigm they are discussed from a scientific perspective, He is three to the Eye of knowledge, The "eyes of knowledge" Shown in the type. (a)Sensory eye of Knowledge (b) Intellectual Eye of knowledge and (c)

Contemplative eye of knowledge . (the eye of sense perception, the eye of intellectual knowledge and the eye pertaining to Samadhi knowledge) one who can transcend the instincts the senses and sink into the tranquil consciousness of the state of Samadhi arises the eye of Wisdom This is stated in the Vibhutipada¹⁵ of patanjalis yoga Sutra. Rishi Arvind considers this level to be the Supermind in the practice of Sense . psychologist Joseph Vrinte says for this Senses of mind .Truth Consciousness free from ignorance, in which the sense of integral yoga never lost¹⁶ .

Self realization of life is not possible until wisdom consciousness arises ignorance obscures the meaning of life. This covering is the cause of the suffering of the world. Samadhi means 'full awakening or full awareness'. (full awareness) in this state of full awareness only the witness state remains. In this state, one is able to see the evil fields of the inner world with the wisdom. Dhritrashtra only heard about the battle but did not see it. because he was blind to knowledge .

On the other hand the path of acquiring knowledge or continuing practice leads to psychological distortion of the seeker. Sometimes before you move forward on the path Of sadness and attain Samadhi or salvation jealousy. Sometimes depression, sometimes Apathy, etc. mental disorders develop. an experienced guru is essential to remove such mental disorders And shape the seeker into a normal Person. This is what ken Wilber Mentions in his book transformation of consciousness about pathology (diagnosis) and Psychotherapy (Psychotherapy)¹⁷ He also divided human consciousness into three levels:(1) Sub consciousness (the State of human consciousness before the creation of Civilization and culture). (2)Self-consciousness (The level of consciousness Created by civilization and culture. This level is what creates the Human personality. (3) Super consciousness it is an artificial pillar coated on the true Consciousness of a person.) Prepersonal Unity, Personal Unity and Transpersonal unity¹⁸ .

Respectively In the first chapter of the Geeta, Psychological problems are expressed through Arjuna . The Second verse to the nineteenth verse of the First chapter can be regarded as 'environmental psychology' in which there are two fierce warring armies .The story is described. Verses 28 to 45 of the first chapter describe Arjuna's mental depression and verses 4 to 6 of the second chapter describe his mental disorder. The treatment of this mental disorder is started by Lord Krishna in the eleventh vers of the second chapter. Fear and anxiety are the main source of depression. among the fears death is the most frightening . This fear of death is the cause of many fears that modern psychology has named anxiety disorders neurosis and they are phobias, panic disorders, and panic

depressive disorder), analyzed the various types of psychotic disorders such as schizophrenia, personality disorders, etc. and developed treatments.

According to Geeta psychology the main cure for mental disorders is self- knowledge. The realization of the inequality of the soul relieves the mental weaknesses of life and inspires infinite action. Therefore. the teaching of The Geeta begins with the Knowledge of the Inequality of the soul, modern psychological medicine also includes, cognitive therapy's to treat mental illness. For the realization of self Knowledge, wisdom must be awakened. So be wise the symptoms are mention in verses 55 to 68 of the second chapter. From this chapter onwards, the theory of the of self. the theory of God, The theory of the Brahman, The theory of the life, the theory of mind, . intelligence. mind, ego. the theory of the body, the theory of karma, the theory of religion, bondage, liberation, meditation, sadness, karma yoga, bhakti yoga and jnana yoga. Above all, the Geeta emphasizes selfless action. this is the only way to attain complete self-surrender yoga. it is in this state of complete surrender that the individual , consciousness become one with the soul of God of the world, freed from the bondage of space time Personality created by civilization and culture in a State of complete egolessness. The Geeta considers the bond of personality to be the bond of religion. Therefore, in order to merge into perfection, he has Imposed the condition of apostasy. This stage is also referred to by ken wilber in his book transformation of consciousness as the 'transpersonal stage' the Geeta analyzes karma, bhakti and jnana yoga as systematic and complementary To each other and combines them into A complete yoga. It is on this basis that Rishi Arvind said the foundation for the practice of 'integral yoga.

Conclusion:

From a review of various aspects we can conclude that Bhagavad Geeta is the oldest 'Manas Granth' in the world and Lord Krishna is the first psychologist in the world. But we Indians have yet to establish this in the word. We have limited the Geeta to devotion and bound its universal and eternal possibilities with emotion. This is the opposite of Geeta worship. Analytical and empirical interpretation and application of the Geeta should be Introduced to make the traditional Method of teaching the Geeta dynamic And practical in today's society. This work requires the cooperation of a class of revered intellectuals besides ordinary devotees and vaishnavas. Only then will it be possible to improve the overall welfare of the Geeta In society and the great Geeta will gain Special status.

Footnotes:

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2. The yoga tradition, P-252. By georg Feuerstein.

3. This is also mentioned in Eliot's is magazine the Griterion
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